
STUDY OF THE PHENOMENON OF GRADUONYMY IN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract.

It is well known that in nature and in society, all events and products are inextricably linked. In particular, the units of linguistics are closely interrelated, they have similarities and differences. Some of their features have been studied, while others are still awaiting study. The same can be said of graduonymy and synonymy. The study of the phenomenon of graduonymy in English and Uzbek linguistics, the main criterion is the decrease or increase of the amount of a sign (event) in a certain direction in determining the gradation, the philosophical foundations of gradation and the scope of its formation, this phenomenon is a link between the types of languages. The scientific views of linguists about all levels of the language, their units, general and special systems are highlighted.

Keywords.

grading, graduonomiya, synonymic relation, semantics, linguistics, lexic-semantics, scientific work, research, phenomenon of gradation.

Introduction

One of the current issues of the field of linguistics is the different aspects of the phenomena of graduonymy and synonymy. This issue was a lively idea that could not find its solution until the 80s of the last century. In the 1980s, linguists began to try to find a solution to this puzzle. R. Safarova in her scientific work, the semantic relations of words are not limited to antonyms, synonyms, and also a view of modern relations was given as species [6]. In our linguistics, synonyms have been sufficiently studied, their properties have been proven by certain scientific researches. But the phenomenon of graduonimia has not been studied to the extent required. The phenomenon of graduonymy as a type of lexeme-semantic relations has been considered since the end of the 80s. Until this time, the phenomenon of gradation was studied within the framework of synonyms. The main reason for this was that words with the characteristic of gradation were given as synonyms in the dictionary of synonyms of the Uzbek language [2]. After researching this issue, it

was learned that graduonymy and synonymy are not the same phenomenon, and the graduable words were distributed into synonymy nests.

It is clear to everyone that all things and events in existence are inextricably linked. In particular, all units in the language are closely related to each other, they have similarities and differences. Some of their features have been studied, while others are still waiting for their research. We can safely say this about the phenomena of graduonymy and synonymy. If synonymy and its specific aspects have been studied a lot, the phenomenon of graduonymy has not been studied to the extent required.

Discussion And Results

Synonymous series is formed by combining the members of the paradigm around one common denotant. In this case, the meaning between the members of the paradigm, the event-events, signs-characteristics that they name, they express exactly one concept. They can be distinguished in their paradigm according to stylistic colors and scope of application.

Even though synonomic relations have a long history in the history of linguistics, like our science, even though thousands and thousands of pages and works have been devoted to the problems of lexical semantics, even though not one, but several dictionaries of synonyms have been compiled. , in the problem of synonyms, there are still many puzzles that need to be solved. Among such issues, the following can be listed: I. The problem of synonyms and double words (cart/cart) II. Synonyms, words with moderate stylistic color and bright stylistic color (yuz/turk, yuz/aft) III. Full and partial synonyms (house/building; yard/house) IV. Synonyms and leveling in the lexical meaning (for example: good~tuzuk~binoyi~in place~soz) V. The issue of linguistic and speech synonyms (friend-friend; friend-lover~jonona~dilbar, mahbuba) [11]. This list could be continued much longer. But that alone is enough for us, and we will limit ourselves to describing the similarities and differences between these two linguistic phenomena, focusing on the issues of lexical synonymy and lexical graduonymy. The study of graduonymy (spiritual gradation) as a special type of inter-word spiritual relations began in the late 80s. In linguistics, until graduonymy was distinguished as a special form of semantic relations between words, the series of words expressing a sign by degree was studied within the framework of synonyms. In the dictionary of synonyms of the Uzbek language, the words whose meanings are graded were given among synonyms in many cases. Of course, since the phenomenon of graduonymy was not specifically distinguished, the words

showing the meaning of the degree were in many cases scattered in different synonymy nests. There were also legitimate reasons for this. Because synonyms include words that are close to each other in meaning.

The leading factor in combining synonomic lines is that the words of the synonomic paradigm have one common denotation (so-called) and differ mainly by stylistic colors and scope of use within their paradigm, while the words of the graduonymic paradigm have different denotations. but the difference between these denotations is not in the qualities of the denotations, but in their quantitative indicators. Therefore, the main difference between synonymy and graduonymy can be shown as follows: the members of the paradigm of words connected by synonymous relations call, express and name the same reality in different ways.

The word graduonymy was used as a linguistic term by R. Safarova and the authors of "Theses of Systemic Lexicology" among the first[4]. Members of the paradigm of words associated with graduonymic relations are connected with relations of increasing or decreasing the same sign in different denotations. At first glance, the boundary between synonymy and graduonymy is clear - if the denotations are the same - synonymy, although the denotations are different, these denotations are the meaning of the words as well as the meaning of the words. if the amount is different, it is called graduonimia. When distinguishing a synonomic series, the linguists' base point is the meaning of the words and the rotation of the reality that these words denote; in graduonymic dictionary lines, it is at the level of the same sign that differs not only from the meaning of the words, but also from the quantitative indicators in the semantic constructions of these words.

It has long been known in linguistics that lexical units form certain gradation lines according to their mutual semantic relations [3]. We can see this in the following example: the signs expressed by the words "hot-cold" are contradictory. Therefore, these words are evaluated as opposite meaning words - antonyms. But it is not difficult to understand that there is a sign-by-sign representation in the warm-hot-hot line. The combination of words with a degree of meaning has a long history in linguistics. Grading can be an event between lexemes, inter-phrases, and between lexemes and phrases (connections). Based on these, it is appropriate to talk about lexical and phraseological graduonymy. Lexical grading is reflected in special graduonymic lines. Therefore, it is necessary to think about the units of this ranking and the relationships between these units.

Nouns have a lot of graduonymic series because they represent the subject. The object appears as a certain set of symbols, and the meaning of symbols in

nouns is an important component of their meaning. Therefore, in the Uzbek language, most specific (concrete) nouns and a number of abstract nouns form graduonymic series. In particular, numerical words are built on the basis of complete graduonymic relationships:

Mm – Sm – dm – metr – km [4]

Graduonymic paradigms are also very common in adjectives. For example, we can see the qualities of color:

Pink (pushti) – reddish (qizg'ish) – red (qizil) – dark red (qirmizi) – darkest red (alvon)

When gradation is formed between the members of the graduonymic paradigm by the increase or decrease of the quantity sign, a known-unknown antonymic meaning is formed between the 1st and the last member of the graduonymic paradigm [8].

Ugly (Xunuk), – (badbashara) – malformat (tasqara) – plain (oddiy).

Hut (Kulba) – shelter (hujra) – house (uy) – cottage (hovli) – castle (qasr) – palace (saroy)

It should be emphasized that since the language is a system, the vocabulary system has a systematic nature, and there is no word (lexeme) in the language that does not have a place in a certain lexical paradigm [10]. The phenomenon of spiritual leveling was not specifically distinguished, and since the words that level the meaning were in many cases absorbed into the composition of synonyms, for example, the words whispering~talking~shouting could not find a place in the dictionary of synonyms. The main factor of distinguishing synonyms and combining words into synonomic paradigms is the exactness of the thing, event, event, symbol, feature that the synonymous words mean, which they name. This sharp difference separates graduonymy from synonymy.

The leading factor in combining synonomic lines is that the words of the synonomic paradigm have one common denotation [9] (so-called), and within their paradigm they differ mainly by stylistic colors, the scope of use, while the words of the graduonymic paradigm have different denotations. but the difference between these denotations is not in the qualities of the denotations, but in their quantities. Therefore, the main difference between synonymy and graduonymy can be shown as follows: the members of the paradigm of words connected by synonymous relations call, express and name the same reality in different ways.

The members of the paradigm of words associated with graduonymic relations are associated with relations of increasing or decreasing the same sign in

different denotations [2]. At first glance, the line between synonymy and graduonymy seems clear - if the denotations are the same - synonymy, if the denotations are different, these denotations are mutual adjectives, as well as the meaning of the words. if the amount is different - it is called graduonimia. When distinguishing the synonomic series, the linguists' base point is the meaning of the words and the rotation of the reality that these words denote; in graduonymic lexical lines, it differs not only in the meaning of words, but also in the level of the same sign, which differs by the quantitative indicators in the semantic constructions of these words.

It has been known for a long time in linguistics that lexical units form certain gradation lines according to their mutual semantic relations. We can see this in the following example: the symbols represented by the words "hot and cold" are contradictory. Therefore, these words are evaluated as words with opposite meanings - antonyms. But it is not difficult to understand that there is a sign-by-sign representation in the warm-hot-hot line. Combining words with a degree of meaning has a long history in linguistics [7]. Grading can be an event between lexemes, inter-phrases, and between lexemes and phrases (connections). Based on these, it is appropriate to talk about lexical and phraseological graduonymy.

Conclusion

Lexical gradation is reflected in special graduonymic lines. Therefore, it is necessary to think about the units of this ranking and the relationships between these units. The most important building block of a gradation series is the increase or decrease of the amount of a common character in it. Therefore, lexemes and phrases in this line form mutual semantic links (connections) according to the singular-plural level of one common sign. The main factor in the structure of the gradunomic series is the fact that one type of semantic sign, with its increase or decrease, has become stable components and components of various lexemes and phrases. So, the lexical level can consist of two or more units. Graduonymy is actually evident in three-membered series. Nevertheless, we should take into account that the sequence (event) can have two members from the linguistic point of view.

REFERENCES:

1. Otaboeva M.R. O'zbek va ingliz tillarida fe'llar graduonimiyasi: Filol. fan. fals.dokt. ... diss. – Andijon, 2022. – B. 15.

2. Gennad'evna T.S. Angliyskie frazeologicheskie yedinisi s gradual'noy semantikoy: lingvokul'turologicheskiy aspekt: Diss. ... kand. filol. nauk. – Donesk, 2018.
3. Orifjonova Sh. "O'zbek tilda lug'aviy graduonimiya" f.f.n. diss. avtoreferat. Toshkent, 1997.
4. Orifjonova Sh. "O'zbek tilida lug'aviy graduonimiya" avtoreferat. – Toshkent 1996; 26 b.
5. Jumabaeva J.Sh. O'zbek va ingliz tillarida leksik graduonimiya: Filol. fan. dokt. ... diss. – Toshkent, 2016.
6. Safarova R. Giponomiya v uzbekskom yazike. Kd. – Tashkent, 1990
7. Eshboev Q. So'zlararo darajalanish o'quv lug'atini tuzish asoslari: Filol. fan. fals.dok. ... diss. avtoref. – Andijon, 2022.
8. Kasimova M.B. "TILSHUNOSLIKDA GRADUONIMIYA HODISASINING O'RGANILISHI": Termiz davlat universiteti mustaqil tadqiqotchisi. ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE. International scientific-online conference, 2022
9. Cruse D.A. Lexical- Semantics.-Camdridge University Press, 1986. 192-196 b
10. Мирзақулов Т. Ўзбек тили морфем парадигматикаси ва синтагматикаси масалалари: Филол. фан. док дисс. автореф – Тошкент, 1994. – Б.42.
11. Shermatova G.Dj. "FE'L SO'Z TURKUMLARIGA OID SO'ZLARDA DARAJALANISH" ARES, volume 2, issue 12, 2021.